

ASSESSMENT OF THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF COMMUNITY BASED MANAGEMENT ORGANIZATIONS IN PROMOTING LITERACY IN UBE SCHOOLS IN KADUNA STATE, NIGERIAⁱ

Hanna Onyi Yusuf^{lii}

Bawa Ribah Mairiga²

¹Dr., Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum,
Faculty of Education Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

²Dr., Department of Arts and Social Science Education
Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

Abstract:

This study assessed the contributions of Community Based Management Organizations in promoting Literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State. The study was carried out with the objectives to assess the contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State, and to find out the relevance of literacy towards community development. The study adopted survey research design with the target population of 4225 headmasters, 411 principals and 5301 teachers in UBE schools in Kaduna State. A sample size of 497 respondents was sampled from the entire population using random sampling technique which consisted of 211 headmasters, 21 principals and 265 teachers. A close ended questionnaire tagged “Contributions of Community Organizations in Promoting Literacy Questionnaire” was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts of the rank of senior lecturer in Measurement and Evaluation, English language and Curriculum. The reliability level of 0.85 was obtained using Cronbach alpha technique. The researcher with the help of three research assistants administered the questionnaire to the respondents. In answering the research questions, frequency counts, mean and standard deviation were used, while Kruskal-Wallis was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.5 level of significance. Finding revealed that community based management organizations contributed in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna

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ⁱⁱ Correspondence: email hannayusuf@yahoo.com

State, and that literacy is relevant and play crucial role in community development. The study concluded that community based management organizations contributed in areas such as advocacy on enrolment, provision of textbooks, notebooks, biros, charts, maps, pictures, flashcards and so on, in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State. Recommendations were put forward among others that community based management organizations should contribute more to the production and distribution of literacy and other instructional materials for UBE schools in Kaduna State. This will help equip pupils with functional literacy skills.

Keywords: community based management organizations, community development, literacy

1. Introduction

Civilization and development are intertwined. Both of them leverage very much on literacy. Literacy is a weapon for liberation from ignorance and diseases. Literacy cannot be isolated from any development agenda as it is the pivot upon which several other programmes rotate. Literacy involves competence in reading and writing and both aspects have a symbiotic effect on each other. In other words, reading helps writing and writing leads to more reading. Literacy is a driver for sustainable development in that it enables greater participation in the labour market; improved child and family health and nutrition; reduces poverty and expands life opportunities (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization– UNESCO, 2015). Beyond its conventional concept as a set of reading, writing and counting skills, literacy is now understood as a means of identification, understanding, interpretation, creation, and communication in an increasingly digital, text-mediated, information-rich and fast-changing world.

In Kaduna State, however, at least 4 million youth and adults still cannot read and write (UNESCO, 2012). This has excluded the low-literate and low-skilled youth and adults from full participation in their communities and societies. The problems of literacy today start very early and with time, the poor condition of writing and reading worsens. At the primary and junior secondary levels, there is corruption fueling the very poor condition of literacy in Kaduna State. Recently, there were press reports of parents caught writing exams for their children. Those parents should have spent time and money to teach their children how to read and write at home rather than impersonate them to cheat. Worse still, some parents do not even encourage enrolment of children in school (Ojaide, 2015).

To advance literacy as an integral part of life-long learning, Community Based Management Organizations (CBMOs) play an important and relevant role in providing services at the local level thereby promoting literacy in primary and junior secondary schools in Kaduna State. The CBMOs according to Mitsue (1999, p.9) promote literacy through proper advocacy on enrolment and education benefits; boosting morale of school staff; raising money for schools; ensuring students' regular attendance and completion; constructing, repairing, and improving school facilities; contributing in labour, materials, land, and funds; recruiting and supporting teachers; forming village education committees to manage schools; actively attending school meetings to learn about children's learning progress and classroom behaviour; helping children with studying; advocating and promoting girls' education; and preparing children's readiness for schooling by providing them with adequate nutrition and stimuli for their cognitive development.

2. Review of Related Literature

Literacy involves a "*continuum of learning in enabling individuals to achieve their goals, to develop their knowledge and potential, and to participate fully in their community and wider society*" (UNESCO, 2004). Literacy is traditionally understood as the ability to read, write, and use arithmetic (Wikipedia, 2017). The concept of literacy is expanding to include skills to access knowledge through technology and ability to assess complex contexts (UNESCO, 2006). A person who travels and resides in a foreign country but is unable to read or write in the language of the host country would also be regarded by the locals as being illiterate. It is argued that literacy is ideological, which means that literacy always exists in a context, in tandem with the values associated with that context (Brian, 2004). Literacy also includes the cultural, political, and historical contexts of the community in which communication takes place (Kress, 2003).

Given that a large part of the benefits of literacy can be obtained by having access to a literate person in the household, some recent literature distinguishes between a "proximate illiterate" and an "isolated illiterate" (McKenna, & Richards, 2003). The former refers to an illiterate person who lives in a household with literates and the latter to an illiterate who lives in a household of all illiterates. What is of concern is that many people in poor communities are not just illiterates but isolated illiterates. However, it is argued that community based management organization can support the quality of education and learning outcomes through their role as instructional partners. Community based management organizations refers to local or grassroots groups of people who have become involved in the planning, research, development,

management and policy making for a community as a whole (Balint, & Mashinya, 2005; Senyk, 2012).

The community based management organizations play an important and relevant role in providing services at the local level. It is a non-profit organisation whose activities are based primarily on volunteer efforts (Chechetto-Salles & Geyer, 2006). This means that CBMOs depend heavily on voluntary contributions for labour, material and financial support in scaling-up functional literacy levels for youth and adults who lack basic literacy skills; and developing literate environments. In addition, community based management organizations are active collaborators in their own children's learning and development. It has to be realised that to sustain progress towards other goals such as community development, employment, poverty reduction, health related programmes, and so forth, attention must be paid to ensuring the acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, manipulative, communicative and life skills as well as the ethical, moral and civic values needed for laying a solid foundation for life-long learning. This study therefore assessed the contributions of Community Based Management Organizations in promoting Literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State.

3. Objectives of the Study

This study was carried out with the following objectives

1. To assess the contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State, and
2. To find out the opinion of respondents regarding the relevance of literacy towards community development.

3.1 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the conduct of the study:

1. What are the contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State?
2. What are the opinions of respondents regarding the relevance of literacy towards community development?

3.2 Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State.
2. There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents regarding relevance of literacy towards community development.

4. Methodology

This study adopted survey research design. The target population of this study comprised of four thousand, two hundred and twenty five (4225) headmasters, four hundred and eleven (411) principals and five thousand three hundred and one (5301) teachers in UBE schools in Kaduna State. A sample size of four hundred and ninety seven (497) respondents were sampled from the entire population using random sampling technique which consisted of two hundred and eleven (211) headmasters, twenty one (21) principals and two hundred and sixty five (265) teachers. A cloze ended questionnaire tagged "Contributions of Community Organizations in Promoting Literacy Questionnaire" was used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section 'A' sought for the demographic information of the respondents, while section 'B' contains 20 items structured in line with the research questions and hypotheses. All the 20 items were structured using four point rating scale of strongly agree, agree, strongly disagree, and disagree. Three experts of the rank of senior lecturer in Measurement and Evaluation, English language and Curriculum validated the instrument. The reliability level of the instrument was found to be 0.85 using Cronbach alpha technique. The researcher with the help of three research assistants administered the questionnaire to the respondents. The questionnaire administered was sorted, tabulated and coded before analysis. In answering the research questions, frequency counts, mean and standard deviation were used while Kruskal-Wallis was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.5 level of significance.

5. Results

This section presents the result of each of the research questions and hypotheses tested. The research questions were answered using frequency counts, mean and standard deviation while Kruskal-Wallis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question One: What are the contributions did community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State?

This question was responded to using frequency counts, response mean and standard deviation. The summary of this analysis is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	SD
1.	Some members of CBMOs volunteer as mentors from outside the school to work alongside teachers during lessons.	194	126	55	122	2.63	1.23
2.	CBMOs provide teaching and learning materials such as text books, notebooks, biros, and so forth in UBE schools.	185	132	106	74	2.62	1.22
3.	Visual aids instructional materials like chart, maps, pictures, flash-cards are provided in UBE schools by the CBMOs.	238	138	72	49	3.13	1.00
4.	CBMOs always encourage students' regular attendance and completion of school.	246	119	38	94	3.04	1.15
5.	CBMO members provide audio-visual materials such as computers, television etc. to promote literacy in UBE schools.	232	164	59	42	3.17	.945
6.	The community based management organisations advocate enrolment of pupils in schools.	171	146	97	83	2.81	1.08
7.	The CBMOs in collaboration with UBE schools head organizes special debate from time to time for students.	133	150	98	116	2.60	1.11
8.	Audio instructional materials like radio sets, audio cassettes are provided in UBE schools by the CBMOs.	188	128	120	61	2.89	1.04
9.	The community based management organisation often meet with schools head to discuss the problems that affect students' learning and suggest ways to resolve them.	272	113	63	49	3.22	1.01
10.	The CBMOs donated adequate fund to UBE schools to ensure that all students are provided with all necessary instructional materials.	170	157	114	56	2.90	1.03
Average Mean						2.90	1.08

Table 1 shows the analysis carried out on the contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State. The table shows the average response mean of 2.90 which is higher than the decision mean of 2.5. This indicates that the response of the participants in respect of the ten items on the table varies but pointed towards a positive direction. The implication of this result is that community based management organizations contributed positively in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State.

Research Question Two: What are the opinions of respondents regarding the literacy towards community development?

This question was responded to using frequency counts, response mean and standard deviation. The summary of this analysis is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Relevance of literacy in community development

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	SD
1.	Literacy permits both male and female citizens to be trained for workforce in the pursuance of community development.	256	150	45	46	3.23	.959
2.	Literacy emphasis on skills-acquisition that enables students set up a proper community development plan.	285	108	55	49	3.26	1.00
3.	Literacy can promote peaceful co-existence among youth in the community.	298	66	85	48	3.27	1.02
4.	Literacy enables students to construct effective solutions their community challenges.	70	262	82	83	3.08	1.12
5.	Literacy skill enables students to make positive contributions towards community development.	103	273	50	71	3.16	1.09
6.	Equipping students with literacy provides them with technical strength and creativity relevant to community development.	306	56	68	67	3.21	1.11
7.	Literacy enables students to exploit opportunities that abound in the society thereby ensuring community development.	202	120	67	108	2.84	1.18
8.	Literacy allow students to demonstrate what they know and can do using a wide range of methods.	222	104	119	52	2.99	1.05
9.	Literacy reduces high rate of poverty, create employment opportunities.	253	131	68	45	3.19	.986
10.	Equipping students with literacy skills promotes community development.	206	83	122	86	2.82	1.15
	Average Mean					3.10	1.06

Table 2 shows the analysis carried out on the relevance of literacy in community development. The table shows the average response mean of 3.10 which is higher than the decision mean of 2.5. This indicates that the response of the participants in respect of the ten items on the table varies but pointed towards a positive direction. The implication of this result is that literacy is relevant and plays an important role in community development.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents regarding the contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State.

Data gathered from the questionnaire administered was analysed using Kruskal-Wallis non parametric statistics. Table 3 present the summary of the analysis.

Table 3: Summary of Kruskal-Wallis test on the contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State

Variable	Group	N	Mean Rank	Chi-square (χ^2)	df	P-value	Decision
Contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State.	Headmasters	211	25.81	21.026	34	0.003	Rejected
	Principals	21	28.18				
	Teachers	265	24.08				
Total		497					

Table 3 revealed the Kruskal-Wallis statistics calculated to determine whether there is statistically difference in contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State. The table shows the group $\chi^2 = 21.026$, $p = 0.001 < 0.05$ at 34 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State is hereby rejected. This result implies that community based management organizations contribute positively in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents regarding relevance of literacy towards community development.

Data gathered from the questionnaire administered was analysed using Kruskal-Wallis non parametric statistics. Table 4 present the summary of the analysis.

Table 4: Summary of Kruskal-Wallis test on the relevance of literacy towards community development

Variable	Group	N	Mean Rank	Chi square (χ^2)	df	P-value	Decision
Relevance of literacy towards community development.	Headmasters	211	65.81	21.026	34	0.001	Rejected
	Principals	21	52.13				
	Teachers	265	32.76				
Total		497					

Table 4 revealed the Kruskal-Wallis statistics calculated to determine whether there is statistically any difference in the opinions of respondents regarding the relevance of literacy towards community development. The table shows the group $\chi^2 = 21.026$, $p = 0.001 < 0.05$ at 34 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents regarding relevance of

literacy towards community development is hereby rejected. This result implies that literacy is relevant and plays an important role in community development.

6. Discussion of Findings

The result of the Kruskal-Wallis statistics on hypothesis one revealed that community based management organizations contribute positively in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the contributions of community based management organizations in promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State was rejected. This result is in accordance with the assertion of Mitsue (1999) that community based management organizations promote literacy through proper advocacy on enrolment and education benefits; boosting morale of school staff; raising money for schools and so forth. Finding of the research conducted by Balint and Mashinya (2005) and Senyk (2012) also revealed that community based management organization supports the quality of education and learning outcomes through their role as instructional partners.

Findings on hypothesis two revealed that literacy is relevant and play crucial role in community development. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents regarding the relevance of literacy towards community development was rejected. This finding agrees with that of UNESCO (2004) that, literacy involves a continuum of learning in enabling individuals to achieve their goals, to develop their knowledge and potential, and to participate fully in their community and wider society. The finding is also in agreement with UNESCO (2015) that literacy is a driver for sustainable development in that it enables greater participation in the labour market, improved child and family health and nutrition, reduces poverty and expands life opportunities thereby promoting community development.

7. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, one can conclude that community based management organizations contributed in no small measure towards promoting literacy in UBE schools in Kaduna State. This is evidenced in their advocacy of enrolment of pupils in schools, provision of teaching and learning materials such as text books, notebooks, biros, and the provision of audio-visual instructional materials like chart, maps, pictures, flash-cards, computers, television and so on, to promote literacy in UBE schools. In addition, literacy has been proved to be relevant towards community

development as it enables students to make effective and positive contributions towards community development. It also provides students with technical strength and creativity relevant to community development.

8. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were put forward that:

1. Community based management organizations should continue to contribute more to the production and distribution literacy and other instructional materials to all UBE schools in Kaduna State. This will help to facilitate pupils' acquisition of functional literacy and numeracy skills.
2. Parents should encourage their children to read widely they should read good newspaper articles, novels, short stories, memories, autobiographies, and other books on different subjects. Such readings will inspire students to express themselves and ultimately improve the quality of their education and learning outcomes.

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